

Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning Program Implementation on the Literacy Improvement Among Elementary School Learners

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the degree of implementation of the ARAL Program and the extent of learners' literacy performance among elementary learners in the Bauan East and Bauan West Sub-Offices, Division of Batangas Province, with the end view of improving instructional practices and learner engagement.

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design using a researcher-made questionnaire to examine the degree of ARAL Program implementation and the extent of learners' literacy performance. The respondents of the study had a total population of 392, from which a sample of 198 learners was drawn. The statistical tools used were frequency, weighted mean, ranking, and Pearson's r correlation coefficient.

Results revealed that the ARAL Program was highly implemented in terms of tutors' competence and administrative support, while implementation in terms of learning resource materials was moderately implemented. In terms of learners' literacy performance, class participation and level of interest were highly manifested, whereas participation in curricular and co-curricular activities was moderately manifested. Furthermore, the relationship between the degree of program implementation and learners' performance was found to be highly significant, indicating that effective utilization of resources, tutor competence, and administrative support positively influence learners' literacy outcomes.

In conclusion, the respondents encountered various challenges in the implementation of the ARAL Program, including limited training, time constraints, low learner motivation, and insufficient learning resources. Nevertheless, a contextualized intervention guide was proposed to enhance the implementation of the ARAL Program and improve learners' literacy performance.

Keywords: *ARAL Program, literacy performance, literacy intervention, reading comprehension, elementary education.*

Introduction

Literacy is widely recognized as one of the strongest indicators of a child's future academic performance and lifelong learning potential. In the Philippine basic education system, the development of proficient readers, particularly in the early grades, remains a national priority, as reading serves as the foundation for learning across subject areas.

Despite its importance, the development of literacy skills among elementary learners remains a persistent concern. Reading comprehension, participation, and learner engagement are essential components of academic success; however, many learners continue to experience difficulties in acquiring foundational literacy skills. Learning gaps brought about by diverse learner needs, limited instructional resources, and disruptions in education have significantly affected learners' academic performance. In response, the Department of Education introduced the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program under the leadership of Sonny Angara to address learning gaps and strengthen foundational skills in literacy and numeracy through targeted and contextualized interventions.

The effective implementation of the ARAL Program depends on instructional delivery, learning resource materials, learner engagement, and teacher support. Teachers play a vital role in ensuring that literacy interventions are learner-centered and responsive to diverse reading needs, while the availability of appropriate instructional materials and collaborative practices further enhances learners' reading development. However, despite ongoing literacy interventions, some learners continue to experience difficulties in reading fluency, comprehension, and participation, highlighting the need to evaluate program effectiveness and identify areas for improvement.

Thus, this study aims to determine how the ARAL Program supports literacy improvement among elementary school learners in the Bauan East and Bauan West Sub-Offices and identifies effective practices and challenges in its implementation. The findings may serve as a basis for strengthening literacy instruction and developing targeted intervention strategies. The output of this study is a contextualized literacy intervention guide aligned with the ARAL Program, designed to support teachers in enhancing learners' reading comprehension, participation, and overall literacy performance.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the implementation of Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program among the elementary school learners at Bauan East and Bauan West Sub-Offices, Division of Batangas Province as basis for the proposed enhancement activities. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the degree of ARAL Program implementation as assessed by the teachers in terms of:

- 1.1. Learning Resource Materials;
- 1.2. Tutors Knowledge; and

- 1.3. Administrative support?
2. How may the extent of manifestation of ARAL program in the learner's performance on literacy be assessed by the respondents with respect to:
 - 2.1. Classroom Participation
 - 2.2. Level of Interest
 - 2.3. Curricular/ Co-curricular Activities
3. Is there a significant relationship between the assessments on the degree of implementation and on the extent of manifestation of ARAL program in the learner's performance on literacy?
4. What are the challenges met by the teachers in implementing the ARAL program?
5. Based on the results of the study, what contextualized literacy intervention guide may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the relationship between the assessment on the degree of ARAL Program implementation and on the extent of manifestation of ARAL Program learners' performance in literacy in the Bauan East and Bauan West Sub-Offices.

Participants

The participants of this study were composed of 392 teachers from the Bauan East and Bauan West Sub-Offices, Division of Batangas Province, from which 198 respondents were selected as the sample size. The selection of respondents was carried out using the stratified random sampling technique with proportionate allocation per school. The sample size was determined through Slovin's formula at a 5 percent margin of error.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire and an unstructured interview to gather data on the implementation of the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program and its impact on the literacy improvement of elementary learners.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) of the Schools Division Office of Batangas Province prior to data gathering. Upon approval, permission letters were forwarded to school principals together with the SDS endorsement. After securing consent, questionnaires were reproduced and distributed to selected elementary teachers in the Bauan East and Bauan West Sub-Offices.

In addition, unstructured interviews were conducted with selected respondents to obtain in-depth information that supplemented the survey data. Informed consent was secured from all participants, which included details on the study's purpose, procedures, confidentiality, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw at any time. Ethical approval and permission from school authorities were also observed.

The study complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensuring the confidentiality and protection of respondents' information. The researcher personally supervised the administration, retrieval, and validation of data from both questionnaires and interviews to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Data Analysis

The study used descriptive statistics (frequency, weighted mean, and ranking) to summarize the respondents' assessments of the degree of ARAL Program implementation and learners' literacy performance. Frequency was used to determine the number of responses for each indicator, while weighted mean was used to compute the average level of responses in terms of program implementation and literacy performance. Ranking was used to identify the most common practices, strategies, and challenges encountered in the implementation of the ARAL Program. Pearson's r was used to determine the significant relationship between the degree of ARAL Program implementation and the extent of learners' literacy performance.

Results

1. Degree of ARAL Program Implementation

1.1 Learning Resource Materials

The table presents the degree of implementation of the ARAL Program in terms of learning resource materials. The overall weighted mean of 3.49, interpreted as Moderately Implemented, indicates that while some components of the program are practiced effectively, there are still notable areas that require improvement to achieve full implementation.

**Degree of ARAL Program Implementation in terms of
Learning Resource Materials**

I. Learning Resources Materials	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. ARAL reading modules are provided on time.	3.57	Highly Implemented	1
2. Learning materials are sufficient to meet learners' literacy needs.	3.48	Moderately Implemented	5.5
3. Materials are relevant to learners' grade-level competencies.	3.46	Moderately Implemented	8

4. The quality of reading and instructional materials is satisfactory.	3.43	Moderately Implemented	9.5
5. Learning resources are easy to use during tutoring sessions.	3.55	Highly Implemented	2.2
6. Materials are updated according to DepEd guidelines.	3.51	Highly Implemented	4
7. Tutors can effectively utilize the provided resources.	3.55	Highly Implemented	2.2
8. Resources promote independent learning among learners.	3.43	Moderately Implemented	9.5
9. Visual and interactive materials are included for better comprehension.	3.47	Moderately Implemented	7
10. The distribution of learning resources is efficient.	3.48	Moderately Implemented	5.5
Composite Mean	3.49	Moderately Implemented	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Highly Implemented, 2.50 – 3.49 = Moderately Implemented, 1.50 – 2.49, = Slightly Implemented, 1.00 – 1.49 = Least Implemente

1.2 Tutors' Knowledge

The table presents the degree of ARAL Program implementation in terms of tutors' knowledge. The overall weighted mean of 3.75, interpreted as Highly Implemented, indicates that tutors possess a strong level of competence and preparedness in delivering instructional support within the program. This suggests that the human resource component of the ARAL Program is a key strength contributing to its effective implementation.

Degree of ARAL Program Implementation in terms of Tutor's Knowledge

II. Tutor's Knowledge	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Demonstrates sufficient understanding of literacy instruction.	3.76	Highly Implemented	4
2. Exhibits familiarity with various teaching strategies for reading.	3.74	Highly Implemented	7.5
3. Addresses learners' individual learning needs effectively.	3.76	Highly Implemented	4
4. Utilizes instructional materials competently.	3.74	Highly Implemented	7.5
5. Implement learner-centered approaches during sessions.	3.75	Highly Implemented	6
6. Displays confidence in guiding learners during ARAL sessions.	3.76	Highly Implemented	4

7. Contributes to the improvement of learners' reading fluency and comprehension.	3.79	Highly Implemented	1
8. Demonstrates knowledge of assessment tools and techniques.	3.72	Highly Implemented	9.5
9. Engages in effective collaboration with classroom teachers.	3.72	Highly Implemented	9.5
10. Observes preparedness and organization in lesson implementation.	3.78	Highly Implemented	2
Composite Mean	3.75	Highly Implemented	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Highly Implemented, 2.50 – 3.49 = Moderately Implemented, 1.50 – 2.49, = Slightly Implemented, 1.00 – 1.49 = Least Implemented

1.3 Administrative Support

The table shows the overall weighted mean of 3.78, interpreted as Highly Implemented, indicates that school administrators play a strong and active role in ensuring the effective delivery of the program. This suggests that leadership, coordination, and institutional support are well-established components contributing to the program's success.

Degree of ARAL Program Implementation in terms of Administrative Support

III. Administrative Support	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. School administration facilitates the smooth implementation of the ARAL Program.	3.81	Highly Implemented	4
2. Administrative staff provide assistance in resource distribution.	3.79	Highly Implemented	6
3. Timely communication from administration supports program execution.	3.77	Highly Implemented	7.5
4. Administration ensures proper scheduling of ARAL sessions.	3.83	Highly Implemented	2
5. Administrative guidance helps tutors in solving classroom issues.	3.80	Highly Implemented	5
6. School leadership encourages teachers' active participation.	3.83	Highly Implemented	2
7. Policies are clear regarding the implementation of the program.	3.83	Highly Implemented	2
8. Administration monitors the progress of ARAL sessions effectively.	3.67	Highly Implemented	9

9. Support from administration contributes to program success.	3.77	Highly Implemented	7.5
10. Administration provides opportunities for tutors' training and development.	3.66	Highly Implemented	10
Composite Mean	3.78	Highly Implemented	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Highly Implemented, 2.50 – 3.49 = Moderately Implemented, 1.50 – 2.49, = Slightly Implemented, 1.00 – 1.49 = Least Implemented

2. Extent of Manifestation of ARAL Program Learners' Performance in Literacy

2.1 Class participation

The overall performance of learners in the ARAL Program on literacy in terms of class participation yielded a weighted mean of 3.50, interpreted as Highly Manifested. This indicates that, in general, students demonstrate active engagement and participation in literacy-related activities, reflecting a positive learning environment that fosters interaction and involvement.

Extent of Learners' Performance in the ARAL Program on Literacy in terms of Class Participation

I. Class Participation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Respond actively during reading sessions.	3.50	Highly Manifested	5
2. Volunteer to answer and share ideas.	3.45	Moderately Manifested	9
3. Engage in group discussions effectively.	3.49	Moderately Manifested	6.5
4. Ask questions to clarify concepts.	3.42	Moderately Manifested	10
5. Participate regularly in literacy activities.	3.55	Highly Manifested	3
6. Show willingness to read aloud.	3.53	Highly Manifested	4
7. Contribute to peer learning.	3.58	Highly Manifested	1
8. Complete assigned tasks on time.	3.49	Moderately Manifested	6.5
9. Demonstrate confidence when participating.	3.47	Moderately Manifested	8
10. Interact positively with the tutor and classmates.	3.57	Highly Manifested	2

Composite Mean	3.50	Highly Manifested	
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Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Highly Manifested, 2.50 – 3.49 = Moderately Manifested, 1.50 – 2.49, = Slightly Manifested, 1.00 – 1.49 = Least Manifested

2.2 Level of interest

The table presents the overall weighted mean of 3.51, interpreted as Highly Manifested, indicates that learners generally demonstrate a strong level of interest and engagement in literacy-related tasks under the ARAL Program. This suggests that the program is effective in fostering positive attitudes toward reading and learning.

Extent of Learners' Performance in the ARAL Program on Literacy in terms of Level of Interest

II. Level of Interest	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Show curiosity in reading activities.	3.49	Moderately Manifested	7
2. Demonstrate motivation to attend and participate in ARAL sessions.	3.49	Moderately Manifested	7
3. Show enthusiasm in completing literacy tasks.	3.49	Moderately Manifested	7
4. Maintain focus during lessons	3.39	Moderately Manifested	10
5. Enjoy engaging with learning materials.	3.51	Highly Manifested	3
6. Demonstrate a positive attitude toward reading.	3.50	Highly Manifested	6
7. Eager to participate in new learning activities.	3.51	Highly Manifested	3
8. Exhibit interest in improving reading skills.	3.52	Highly Manifested	2
9. Willingly take part in follow-up activities.	3.51	Highly Manifested	3
10. Show consistent effort to achieve reading goals.	3.66	Highly Manifested	1
Composite Mean	3.51	Highly Manifested	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Highly Manifested, 2.50 – 3.49 = Moderately Manifested, 1.50 – 2.49, = Slightly Manifested, 1.00 – 1.49 = Least Manifested

2.3 Curricular and Co-curricular Activities

The extent of learners' performance in literacy as reflected in their participation in curricular and co-curricular activities under the ARAL Program has overall weighted mean of 3.47, interpreted as Moderately Manifested, indicates that while learners are engaged in various literacy-related activities, their level of participation and performance is not yet maximized and requires further enhancement.

Extent of Learners' Performance in the ARAL Program on Literacy in terms of Curricular / Co-curricular Activities

III. Curricular / Co-Curricular Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Participate in classroom literacy activities.	3.48	Moderately Manifested	3
2. Engage in school-organized reading programs.	3.46	Moderately Manifested	6.5
3. Take part in literacy-based competitions or projects.	3.45	Moderately Manifested	8
4. Apply reading skills across other subject areas.	3.58	Highly Manifested	1
5. Contribute to group activities related to literacy.	3.47	Moderately Manifested	4.5
6. Attend reading-related workshops or events.	3.37	Moderately Manifested	10
7. Complete home-based literacy assignments.	3.43	Moderately Manifested	9
8. Practice reading skills independently.	3.47	Moderately Manifested	4.5
9. Demonstrate the integration of literacy in co-curricular tasks.	3.51	Highly Manifested	2
10. Show improvement through participation in curricular and co-curricular activities.	3.46	Moderately Manifested	6.5
Composite Mean	3.47	Moderately Manifested	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Highly Manifested, 2.50 – 3.49 = Moderately Manifested, 1.50 – 2.49, = Slightly Manifested, 1.00 – 1.49 = Least Manifested

3. Relationship Between the Assessments on the Degree of Implementation and on the Extent of Manifestation of ARAL Program Learners' Performance on Literacy

Relationship Between the Assessment on the Degree of Implementation in terms of Learning Resource Materials and the Extent of Manifestation of ARAL Program Learners' Literacy Performance

Learning Resource Materials	r- value	p- value	Decision Ho	Verbal Interpretation
A. Class Participation	0.483	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant
B. Level of Interest	0.390	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant
C. Curricular/ Co- Curricular Activities	0.446	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant

Correlation is at 0.01 level (2-tailed test)

The table presents the relationship between Learning Resource Materials and learners' literacy performance in terms of Class Participation, Level of Interest, and Curricular/Co-Curricular Activities. Findings reveal that all indicators obtained p-values of less than 0.001, which are lower than the 0.01 level of significance; hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates a statistically significant relationship between Learning Resource Materials and learners' literacy performance. Moreover, the correlation coefficients reveal moderate positive relationships, suggesting that improved learning resources are associated with better learner engagement and participation. This implies that the availability and effective utilization of instructional materials play a vital role in enhancing learners' literacy development.

Relationship Between the Assessment on the Degree of Implementation in terms of Tutors' Knowledge and the Extent of Manifestation of ARAL Program Learners' Literacy Performance

Tutors Knowledge	r- value	p- value	Decision Ho	Verbal Interpretation
A. Class Participation	0.489	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant
B. Level of Interest	0.440	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant
C. Curricular/ Co- Curricular Activities	0.467	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant

Correlation is at 0.01 level (2-tailed test)

The findings shown in the relationship between Tutors' Knowledge and learners' literacy performance in terms of Class Participation, Level of Interest, and Curricular/Co-Curricular Activities. Findings show that all p-values are less than 0.001, which are below the 0.01 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates a statistically significant relationship between tutors' knowledge and learners' literacy performance. Furthermore, the correlation coefficients show moderate positive relationships, implying that higher tutor competence is associated with improved learner engagement and participation. This suggests that tutors' instructional skills and knowledge play an important role in enhancing learners' literacy outcomes.

Relationship Between the Assessment on the Degree of Implementation in terms of Administrative Support and the Extent of Manifestation of ARAL Program Learners' Literacy Performance

Administrative Support	r- value	p- value	Decision Ho	Verbal Interpretation
A. Class Participation	0.478	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant
B. Level of Interest	0.472	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant
C. Curricular/ Co- Curricular Activities	0.446	<0.001	Reject	Highly Significant

Correlation is at 0.01 level (2-tailed test)

Table 10 presents the relationship between Administrative Support and learners' literacy performance in terms of Class Participation, Level of Interest, and Curricular/Co-Curricular Activities. Findings reveal that all indicators obtained p-values of less than 0.001, which are below the 0.01 level of significance; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates a statistically significant relationship between administrative support and learners' literacy performance. In addition, the correlation coefficients revealed moderate positive relationships, suggesting that stronger administrative support is associated with better learner engagement and participation. This implies that effective leadership, coordination, and institutional support are essential in strengthening literacy program implementation.

These findings implied that when learning resources are adequately provided and effectively utilized, tutors are competent in delivering instruction, and administrative support is strong and consistent, learners are more likely to actively participate, show greater interest, and engage in both curricular and co-curricular literacy activities.

4. Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the ARAL Program

The table presents the challenges encountered in the implementation of the ARAL Program, with the overall composite mean of 2.77, interpreted as Agree. This indicates that learners, educators, and program implementers generally experience notable difficulties that affect the program's smooth execution.

Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the ARAL Program

I. Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the ARAL Program	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Lack of sufficient learning materials or resources for literacy activities.	2.78	Agree	5
2. Limited training or professional development on ARAL Program implementation.	2.98	Agree	1
3. Time constraints in completing ARAL Program activities.	2.97	Agree	2
4. Low learner motivation or engagement in literacy tasks.	2.85	Agree	3
5. Limited support from school administration or colleagues.	2.53	Agree	10
6. Difficulty in aligning ARAL activities with the Curriculum standards.	2.71	Agree	7
7. Insufficient opportunities for hands-on or practical literacy activities.	2.82	Agree	4
8. Difficulty in maintaining learner engagement during ARAL Program activities.	2.77	Agree	6
9. Difficulty in managing learners during ARAL Program sessions.	2.65	Agree	8
10. Difficulty in monitoring, assessing, and evaluating learners' literacy progress.	2.60	Agree	9
Composite Mean	2.77	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree, 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree, 1.50 – 2.49, = Disagree, 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

5. Proposed Contextualized Intervention Guide

The proposed contextualized intervention guide were designed to strengthen the implementation of the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program and to improve learners' literacy performance. Recognizing that literacy is a foundational skill essential for learning across all subject areas, these activities aim to support learners in developing reading and writing competencies while maximizing the effectiveness of the ARAL Program.

The Contextualized Literacy Intervention Guide presents a structured set of learner- and teacher-centered interventions designed to address identified concerns in the ARAL Program and strengthen learners' literacy performance. It consists of seven interconnected components, KwentoDetectives, BasaStars, ARAL Care Hub, Brain Buddies, BookChampions, Level-Up Mambabasa, and GuroCollab which are grounded on contextualized, meaningful, and learner-

responsive approaches. Each component targets specific literacy needs while promoting active engagement, collaboration, and differentiated instruction among learners and teachers. Overall, the guide provides a systematic and practical framework that supports improved literacy outcomes through relevant and context-based strategies.

Proposed Contextualized Intervention Guide

Areas of Concern	Goals/ Objectives	Enhancement Activities (Intervention)	Success Indicators
Degree of ARAL Program Implementation – Learning Resources <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources promote independent learning among learners. 2. The quality of reading and instructional materials is satisfactory. 3. Materials are relevant to learners' grade-level competencies 	To enhance the quality, relevance, and accessibility of learning resources in the ARAL Program to support learners' literacy development.	#Kwento Detectives – Structured reading sessions using leveled and contextualized texts followed by comprehension and reflection tasks.	Increased availability and utilization of appropriate reading materials; improved learner comprehension; accurate responses to comprehension questions.
Degree of ARAL Program Implementation – Tutors' Knowledge <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engages in effective collaboration with classroom teachers. 2. Demonstrate knowledge of assessment tools and techniques. 3. Utilized instructional materials 	To strengthen tutors' knowledge and skills in collaboration, assessment practices, and the effective use of instructional materials in the ARAL Program.	BasaStars – Interactive read-aloud sessions that enhance instructional delivery, improve the use of assessment tools and techniques, and promote effective collaboration between tutors and classroom teachers through guided practice and reflection.	Strengthened collaboration with classroom teachers, enhanced use of assessment tools and techniques, and more effective utilization of instructional materials during ARAL sessions.

competently. Degree of ARAL Program Implementation – Administrative Support 1. Administration provides opportunities for tutors’ training and development. 2. Administration monitors the progress of ARAL sessions effectively. 3. Support from administration contributes to program success.	To strengthen administrative support in providing training opportunities, effective monitoring, and continuous assistance to ensure the successful implementation of the ARAL Program.	ARAL Care Hub – School-based administrative support system that conducts regular monitoring of ARAL sessions, provides feedback to tutors, and facilitates training and professional development opportunities to strengthen program implementation.	Improved frequency and quality of administrative monitoring, increased provision of training and professional development opportunities for tutors, and stronger implementation support that leads to more effective and organized ARAL sessions.
Learners’ Performance in Literacy – Class Participation 1. Ask questions to clarify concepts. 2. Volunteer to answer and share ideas. 3. Demonstrate confidence	To increase learners’ active participation in literacy-related activities and discussions through collaborative and interactive learning experiences.	Brain Buddies – Think-Pair-Share and peer collaboration activities that encourage learners to discuss ideas, ask questions, and share responses in a supportive group setting.	Increased frequency and quality of participation, improved confidence in oral expression, and enhanced group interaction during literacy activities.
Learners’ Performance in Literacy – Level of Interest 1. Maintain focus during lessons. 2. Show curiosity in reading activities. 3. Demonstrate motivation to attend and	To increase learners’ motivation and interest in literacy by providing engaging, interactive, learning activities that sustain attention, encourage active participation, and foster positive	#BookChampions - Reading contests, storytelling events, and word games that encourage active participation and make literacy activities more engaging and enjoyable for learners.	Increased engagement in reading activities; consistent task completion; improved confidence in expressing ideas

participate in ARAL sessions.	attitudes toward reading and learning.		
<p>Learners' Performance in Literacy – Curricular/Co-Curricular Activities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Attend reading-related workshops or events. 2. Complete home-based literacy assignments. 3. Take part in literacy-based competitions or projects. 	<p>To promote learners' active involvement in literacy-related curricular and co-curricular activities through differentiated and meaningful learning experiences.</p>	<p>Level-Up Mambabasa – Progressive and differentiated reading and writing activities that match learners' levels to encourage active participation and improve literacy performance.</p>	<p>Increased participation in literacy activities; improved reading performance; recognition of learner achievements.</p>
<p>Challenges Encountered by Teachers – Instructional Collaboration & Differentiation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Limited support from administration or colleagues. 2. Difficulty in monitoring, assessing and evaluating learners' literacy progress. 3. Difficulty in managing learners during ARAL Program sessions. 	<p>To strengthen teacher collaboration and enhance the implementation of contextualized literacy instruction through shared practices and collaborative professional development.</p>	<p>GuroCollab – Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions where teachers collaborate, share best practices, and develop instructional strategies, assessment tools, and classroom management techniques to improve ARAL implementation.</p>	<p>Improved teacher collaboration; increased use of shared instructional strategies; enhanced quality of literacy instruction and materials.</p>

Discussion

The study found that the ARAL Program was generally highly implemented in terms of tutors' knowledge and administrative support, indicating strong teacher competence and active involvement of school administrators in program delivery. However, learning resource materials were only moderately implemented, suggesting the need for further improvement in the availability, quality, and sufficiency of instructional resources to better support literacy instruction.

In terms of learners' literacy performance, the results revealed that class participation and level of interest were highly manifested, showing that learners are actively engaged and motivated during ARAL sessions. Meanwhile, curricular and co-curricular activities were moderately manifested, indicating limited participation in enrichment activities beyond regular classroom-based literacy instruction.

The study also revealed a highly significant relationship between the degree of ARAL Program implementation and learners' literacy performance. This indicates that effective implementation of the program is supported by competent tutors, adequate resources, and strong administrative support is positively influences learners' literacy development in terms of participation, interest, and engagement.

Furthermore, the implementation of the ARAL Program was found to be affected by several challenges, including limited training, time constraints, low learner motivation, and insufficient learning resources. These challenges suggest the need to strengthen teacher capacity, improve resource provision, and enhance learner engagement strategies to ensure more effective program implementation.

Based on these findings, a contextualized intervention guide was developed to address the identified gaps and challenges. The guide is designed to strengthen ARAL Program implementation by improving instructional practices, supporting teachers, and enhancing learners' literacy development through structured and learner-centered strategies.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the ARAL Program is generally effectively implemented in terms of tutors' knowledge and administrative support, while learning resource materials require further improvement. Learners demonstrate strong literacy performance in class participation and level of interest, but limited engagement in curricular and co-curricular activities. A significant relationship was also found between ARAL Program implementation and learners' literacy performance, indicating that better implementation leads to improved literacy outcomes. However, challenges such as limited training, time constraints, insufficient resources, and low learner motivation affect program effectiveness.

To further enhance the implementation of the ARAL Program, it is recommended that school administrators provide continuous training and professional development for teachers and tutors. Adequate and high-quality learning resources should also be developed and distributed to support literacy instruction. Teachers are encouraged to employ more engaging and differentiated strategies to sustain learner interest and participation. Moreover, strengthening support systems and allocating sufficient time for ARAL activities may help address implementation challenges. Future researchers may conduct similar studies in other contexts or explore additional variables that may influence literacy development.

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